

FracRisk

Reporting form for deliverables

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Deliverable summary text:	
<p>Seismic noise data recorded at Preese Hall during hydraulic fracturing operations was uploaded onto the FracRisk shared drive and made available on the FracRisk website by 30 April 2016.</p> <p>The attached report provides a description of the data and of the structure of the shared directory.</p>	
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Preese Hall seismic noise data

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Directory PREESE_HALL on the FracRisk shared drive contains seismic ambient noise and event data recorded in 2011 during hydraulic fracturing operations at Preese Hall. This document is intended to provide an overview of the data and of the structure of this directory and its subdirectories.

Data ownership

The raw data in subdirectories `EVENTS` and `NOISE/MINISEED` were acquired and are currently owned by the British Geological Survey (BGS). Any use of this data, of the processed data in subdirectory `NOISE/SAC`, and of the instrument response files in directory `RESP`, must acknowledge the BGS as the source of the data and response files.

Directory structure

The data in this directory is organised as follows:

- **SCRIPTS**: this directory contains script `proc_data.sh`, which was written by Erica Galetti and used to produce the processed data contained in `NOISE/SAC` from the raw data in `NOISE/MINISEED`. It can be modified in order to re-process the data using different processing parameters (e.g., defining a different filter while removing the instrument response).
- **NOISE**: this directory contains seismic ambient noise data recorded by 4 seismic stations near Preese Hall for 4–6 months in 2011, and contains 2 subdirectories:
 - `MINISEED` contains raw data in miniseed format (no processing applied)
 - `SAC` contains processed data in SAC format. Processing was carried out using script `proc_data.sh` in directory `SCRIPTS`, and included removing mean, trend and instrument response, and tapering the edges of the seismic traces. These are standard processing steps when working with noise data, and more details can be found in Bensen et al. (2007). This subdirectory may also contain a series of text files which highlight if errors or warnings came up while processing the data. Note that the data were filtered using a tapered filter while removing the instrument response (see lines 52–56 in `proc_data.sh`).
- **EVENTS**: this directory contains seismic traces of events originating in Preese Hall and recorded by a number of seismic stations belonging to the BGS network GB. The data are in miniseed format and can be ‘unpacked’ using program `mseed2sac` to produce a series of `.SAC` files which can be read using the Seismic Analysis Code (SAC) or Matlab.
- **STATIONS**: this directory contains stations information:

- `GB_dataless.dseed` is the dataless seed file containing station and response information for permanent GB stations
- `rdseed.stations` is the stations summary file obtained from `GB_dataless.dseed` using `rdseed`
- `stations.dat` contains the geographical coordinates of permanent and temporary (Preese Hall) stations in the GB network
- `mseed2sac-2.0`: this directory contains a pre-compiled version of program `mseed2sac`, which can be used to convert miniseed files to SAC format. Any new version of the program and additional information can be found on the `mseed2sac` page.

Data quality control

Raw data (in directories `EVENTS` and `NOISE/MINISEED`) and processed data (in directory `NOISE/SAC`) have only been subjected to a minimal amount of quality control, and further QC should be carried out when the data is used. Such QC measures should include checks for instrument abnormalities and glitches (e.g., see files `2011-09-12-1800-00M.BAVH_HHE.SAC` and `2011-09-12-1900-00M.BAVH_HHE.SAC` and their miniseed counterparts for an example of instrument-related abnormalities).

Useful software

- `SAC`: <http://ds.iris.edu/ds/nodes/dmc/software/downloads/sac/101-6a/>
- `mseed2sac`: <http://ds.iris.edu/ds/nodes/dmc/software/downloads/mseed2sac/2-0/>
- `rdseed`: <http://ds.iris.edu/ds/nodes/dmc/software/downloads/rdseed/5-3-1/>

Contact

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References

Bensen, G. D., Ritzwoller, M. H., Barmin, M. P., Levshin, A. L., Lin, F., Moschetti, M. P., Shapiro, N. M., & Yang, Y., 2007. Processing seismic ambient noise data to obtain reliable broad-band surface wave dispersion measurements, *Geophysical Journal International*, **169**(3), 1239–1260.